

DEVELOPMENT OF THE PROJECT OF MODULAR PREFABRICATED BUILDINGS

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Abstract

The issues of working design with the construction of modular prefabricated buildings, with the minimization of cold bridges are revealed. Cold bridges are typical for prefabricated buildings with inadequate attention to the design of both load-bearing metal and enclosing structures, as well as their connections. Connections should not pass through its cross section both zero and negative temperatures. As a result, an original project of two modular buildings was developed from easily prefabricated metal structures and wall structures with light mineral wool filling. This project is also intended for sharply continental regional natural and climatic conditions (regardless of the geographical location on the territory of Republic of Kazakhstan – south-eastern Republic of Kazakhstan, central, eastern or western Republic of Kazakhstan. In winter, natural and climatic conditions are similar in these areas). As a result of this study, it was found that the developed project meets the requirements of thermal insulation – at the interface of the supporting and enclosing structures. The thermal insulation requirements of the above structures are important to eliminate the dew point and consequently the formation of moisture and mold in all structures. In turn, mold and other microorganisms, as studies show, adversely affect the health and normal stay of people in the premises, both during the night and during the day. Many developers do not consider these factors in prefabricated buildings. These buildings are intended for various industries. For example, in healthcare, these are mobile hospitals. In military camps – buildings of temporary residence as barracks, etc.

Keywords: modular prefabricated buildings, load-bearing structures, metal profile, enclosing structures, microclimate.

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1. Introduction

Modular prefabricated buildings do not lose their relevance in modern architecture and construction, in view of such main advantages as: high speed and all-weather installation, lower cost compared to traditional construction methods. As a rule, unified elements of modular buildings are manufactured at the factory, with further assembly at the construction site.

In general, the modular design method in the production of architecture and construction products can be regarded as one of the highest forms of activity in the field of standardization. The research methods in this article were based on the unification of the structural elements of structural products, as well as on the methods of measuring drawings of building spots, on the basis of tacheometric equipment, etc. Thanks to these methods, it was possible to obtain geometrically accurate structural products at the metal structures manufacturer.

The purpose of this article is to study the development of a project for a modular prefabricated building, taking into account the speed and ease of construction, the cost-effectiveness of pro-

duction and installation of structures, as well as the creation of post-and-beam units of structures connecting enclosing sandwich panels, while minimizing heat loss in the form of cold bridges. To achieve this goal, the following tasks are defined:

- to develop unified load-bearing structures of a prefabricated modular building with simple and quick installation;
- unified load-bearing structures must have a profile that would allow tightly connecting ceiling and wall sandwich panels;
- unified post-beam profile should be able to exclude the formation of cold bridges as much as possible.

At the present stage in construction practice, such issues of modular prefabricated construction as:

- optimization strategies in overcoming key limitations in the construction of modular prefabricated structures [1];
- efficiency of prefabricated building systems [2];
- modular construction technology [3];
- manufacturing technology of prefabricated structures [4];
- impact of prefabrication on the profitability of modular construction, in comparison with traditional methods [5];
- comparative study of prefabricated and traditional construction [6];
- obstacles to the development of prefabricated construction [7];
- high-rise construction of modular buildings [8];
- review of the performance of prefabricated building systems [2];
- optimization of structures of prefabricated buildings [9] and many others.

The above scientific sources substantiate the issues of production, technological, economic and other aspects of prefabricated modular buildings. While, in this article, emphasis is placed on such aspects as: the creation of conjugation structures for enclosing mineral wool sandwich panels, with the elimination of the penetration of the cold of the external environment into the premises of prefabricated buildings, with an emphasis on energy saving. These aspects are quite relevant for the construction of prefabricated modular buildings in the winter climatic conditions of the region.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, the construction of modular prefabricated buildings is at the initial stage of its development. Of the well-known modular buildings built in the country, low-rise buildings of frame structures made of light thin-walled metal structures of the Energy company can be noted [10].

2. Materials and methods

Since 2016, the architectural bureau of the Kazakh Leading Academy of Architecture and Civil Engineering has completed several completed projects of modular canteen buildings for military units.

In the proposed modular system of prefabricated elements, in contrast to the common container type (**Fig. 1**), such advantages of the first option are indicated as:

- simple installation of metal structures;
- simplified transportation of disassembled structures, in contrast to the cumbersome and more costly transportation of containers.

The bearing post-and-beam profile indicated later in the article, in the studied projects of prefabricated modular buildings, was made of carbon steel grade S 235 JR. Also, this profile was taken in accordance with the standards and requirements of the Republic of Kazakhstan on the physical and mechanical properties of steel and their calculated values, with an elastic modulus equal to: $E = 210 \text{ kN/mm}^2$ [11]. After the development of the project of this prefabricated modular building and the interface nodes of the post-beam profile, it became possible to submit these nodes for patenting. Currently, documentation is being developed for submitting these units of load-bearing structures, with interfacing enclosing sandwich panels, for an application for patenting.

Fig. 1. Main advantages and disadvantages of two modular systems

3. Results and discussion

From July to December 2020, two modular buildings were designed and built. These modular buildings were intended for the military unit. They were located in the suburban area of the metropolis of Almaty. On the west side. According to the terms of reference, the buildings being designed and under construction (barracks and headquarters) had to meet such basic requirements as:

- simplicity and all-weather assembly of one-story buildings in the field;
- enclosing structures made of wall and ceiling sandwich panels (with mineral wool thermal insulation 120 and 150 mm thick);
- post-beam system of the supporting frame with the maximum elimination of cold bridges, since many contractors erected and handed over buildings that during operation had condensate inside at the interfaces of wall, floor and ceiling structures.

The natural and climatic conditions near the Shemolgan settlement (Almaty region), in contrast to the metropolis, are characterized by more severe conditions. In winter, the area is characterized by strong cold winds. The natural and climatic features of this area are explained, in contrast to calm Almaty, by the active movements of air masses in the indicated open steppe spaces, between the gorges of the Zailiysky Alatau ridge and the Kapshagai reservoir located in the northeast.

Taking into account the conditions – the terms of reference and the natural and climatic data of the construction site, the designers were faced with the task of developing two modular buildings with the following features:

- load-bearing post-and-beam structures connecting enclosing sandwich panels should have been designed to minimize the passage of cold in winter and demi-season;
- manufacturability and ease of assembly of structures without wet processes during the cold period;
- mobility and lightness of structures during transportation;
- the strength of structures and their joints that can withstand both the passage of cold and sufficiently strong wind currents and seismic loads.

To solve design problems related to the simplicity and manufacturability of the installation of load-bearing and enclosing structures, with the minimization of heat leakage of the technical

specifications and the manufacturability of the process of installation of load-bearing and enclosing structures, the designers developed a unified profile used for both racks and crossbars (**Fig. 2**). This profile, into which the wall enclosing sandwich panels are «threaded», has a dual function. It effectively works in compression (in racks-columns), in bending and torsion (in girder beams). And also, due to the small thickness (2–2.5 mm), (2.5 mm); it does not allow the penetration of cold at the junction of the profile with wall and ceiling structures of sandwich panels. The thickness of the wall and ceiling sandwich panels (made of significantly thermally insulated rigid mineral wool boards) is 120 and 150 mm, respectively.

Thus, the profile, receiving thermal exposure from sandwich panels of considerable thickness, does not allow the penetration of cold through the enclosing structures of walls and ceilings. Thickness of enclosing wall panels – 120 mm, ceiling enclosing panels – 150 mm. Therefore, they exceed the physical dimensions of the supporting post-and-beam profile (2.5 mm) by 48 and 60 times, respectively. Due to this, a significant thermal mass of sandwich panels in comparison with the supporting profile prevents the penetration of cold into the designed buildings. When the dew point is cut off, even in severe frosts. On the first half of the enclosing structures, from the outer edge of the outer walls and ceilings.

Fig. 2. Wall and ceiling sandwich panels (thickness 120 and 150 mm, respectively) are «sewn» into the supporting metal profile (2–2.5 mm thick), (2.5 mm) during installation

The bearing post-beam profile was conceived with a complex configuration (**Fig. 3**). In order to give it the necessary strength in compression, bending and torsion. These strength characteristics of the profile (made according to our drawings) were calculated by the manufacturer using a special computer software product Autodesk LIRA. The central compressive force on the profile turned out: $N = 2180$ kN; maximum design bending moment $M_{\max} = 539.5$ kN·m. Also, this profile is optimal for rigid fastening of enclosing sandwich panels.

In plan, the designed headquarters buildings and barracks have a rectangular configuration with overall dimensions along the axes – 14×17.045 m and 14.46×56.005 , respectively (**Fig. 4, 5**). At the same time, for ease of installation, without the use of lifting mechanisms (light weight of optimally sized racks and beams), the pitch of the columns in the longitudinal direction was 2.435 m, and in the transverse direction – from 2.48 to 3.025 m and 4.8 m.

Fig. 3. Post-beam unified profile of complex configuration for rigid fastening of enclosing sandwich panels; as well as giving, with its insignificant thickness, compressive strength (racks), bending and torsion (beams)

Fig. 4. Plan of the headquarters building

Floor structures for eliminating cold bridges consisted of a «pie» (**Fig. 6**), which included:
– a metal profile in the form of the letter omega (profiled in this form for rigidity and bending strength), resting on the channels of the floor base;

And thus, they made up a solid heat-insulated, rectangular parallelepiped in plan, with a rigid frame seismic-resistant system of metal columns and crossbars integrated into it.

Fig. 7. Structures from sandwich panels: *a* – 3D-scheme of enclosing sandwich panels in the bearing profiles of racks and beams; *b* – the device of a gable roof on the top of the beams and rafters (from galvanized profiled sheet)

These modular headquarters buildings (**Fig. 8, 9**) and barracks were assembled according to the projects under consideration by the contractor (with heating networks) in early December 2020 and were tested, with operation until mid-April 2021 (end of the heating period). During operation, a comfortable average temperature of +24 degrees Celsius was maintained inside the building. At all joints of load-bearing racks and beams; and enclosing wall and ceiling structures, no traces of condensate were found. This designed and built modular prefabricated type can have not only an administrative and economic purpose, but also residential functions for non-permanent residence, such types of structures as hostels, barracks and shift houses.

To evaluate these modular buildings in terms of thermal characteristics, below is a thermal calculation of enclosing structures. The thermotechnical calculation of load-bearing structures, taking into account cold bridges, is planned to be carried out in further studies when financing development work (including the use of a thermal imager). Several subsoil users are interested in these experimental design technologies, which intend to build seasonal prefabricated housing and shift camps.

Fig. 8. Photo of the designed and built headquarters building

Fig. 9. Examples of mounted interiors: *a* – photo of the mounted headquarters corridor; *b* – photo of one of the mounted headquarters rooms

Thermotechnical calculation of enclosing structures. Initial data:

– thermal conductivity of structural layers: λ_1-50 ; λ_3-50 (metal profile, steel), construction thickness: $\delta_1-0.002$; $\delta_3-0.002$ m;

– thermal conductivity of the insulation: $\lambda_2-0.043$, thickness of the insulation $\delta_{2ut}-0.12$ m.

The climate parameters of the Almaty region are taken from regional standards for climatology [12]:

– coefficient of heat absorption of the inner surface $\alpha_v = 8.7 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{°C})$;

– heat transfer coefficient of the outer surface $\alpha_n = 23 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{°C})$;

– temperature of the heating period $t_{heat} - 2.2 \text{ °C}$;

– duration of the heating period $Z_{heat} = 168$ days;

– type of thermal insulation: mineral wool;

– thermal conductivity coefficient of insulation $\lambda_{in} = 0.043 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{°C})$;

– internal and external air temperature $\tau_{in} = 21 \text{ °C}$; $\tau_{out} = -23 \text{ °C}$;

– DHHP – degree hours of the heating period:

$$\text{DHHP} = (t_{in} - t_{heat}) \cdot z_{heat} = 3898.$$

Required heat transfer resistance:

$$R_{0r} = 2.76 \text{ (m}^2 \cdot \text{°C)/W [13].}$$

The solution. Heat transfer resistance:

$$\begin{aligned} R &= (1/\alpha_{in} + \delta_1/\lambda_1 + \delta_{2in}/\lambda_{in} + \delta_3/\lambda_3 + 1/\alpha_{out}) = \\ &= (1/8.7 + 0.002/50 + 0.12/0.043 + 0.002/50 + 1/23) = 2.95 \text{ (m}^2 \cdot \text{°C)/W.} \end{aligned}$$

The resulting heat transfer resistance is higher than the required heat transfer resistance $R > R_{0r}$, therefore: the constructions of the walls of the given modular assemblies have high heat-insulating properties, in comparison with the normative values of the thermal resistance.

Recently, there are a number of scientific works in the Kazakh scientific community, where it is possible to note separately the work investigating energy consumption, when energy

conservation becomes relevant in the region, combined with mathematical modeling of climatic parameters [14]. This also applies to prefab modular structures. Often in prefab modular buildings, due to their rapid construction, insufficient attention is paid to energy saving and calculation of energy efficiency parameters.

In addition to significant heat-insulating qualities, the considered insulating sandwich panels and metal structures have certificates of compliance with hygienic parameters. The main enclosing building material for the walls and ceilings in this project of a prefabricated modular building are sandwich panels with mineral wool filling, with a shell made of thin (2 mm) profiled metal sheets. These materials, having hygienic certificates, correspond to the Technical Regulation of the Republic of Kazakhstan: «Requirements for the safety of built and constructed, construction materials and products» [15].

The advantage of the architectural and structural solutions proposed in this study consists, first of all, in the development of a special metal profile in the rack-and-beam system of prefabricated buildings. This metal profile, with a complex configuration, allows to connect wall and ceiling sandwich panels, as well as floor structures. Moreover, the specified connections have the ability to prevent heat leakage from the internal spaces of the buildings under consideration.

Boundaries and special conditions of the proposed solutions are related to the load-bearing constructions of the assembled structures. When the main requirement for load-bearing structures from the proposed complex metal profile is their compressive and bending strength. Also, in earthquake-prone areas, it is necessary to limit the storeys of prefabricated buildings to two.

The development of this research consists in the further creation of experimental and design developments related to the supporting and enclosing structures of the buildings. Experimental and design developments should be directed, in particular, to the study of energy-saving characteristics of load-bearing racks and beams, including the use of the latest equipment, including thermal imagers. The theoretical aspects of prospective studies on this topic are also the development of conceptual models of modular prefabricated buildings for various natural and climatic regions of the Kazakhstan region. And also for various landscapes of the territory of the country – with flat steppe or hilly, foothills and mountainous terrain.

4. Conclusions

Thus, the presented projects have specially developed nodes. These nodes show the coupling of load-bearing and enclosing structures. These nodes also give the possibility of erecting one-story modular buildings without the formation of cold bridges. Moreover, the construction process takes place in field all-weather conditions, without the use of lifting mechanisms.

The experience of building the first building of this type showed the real terms of its construction. They made one, one and a half months. The cost of construction and assembly works was 40 % of the cost of traditional buildings (with a reinforced concrete frame and walls made of brick and aerated concrete). At the same time, the cost of construction of this first building, in comparison with similar low-rise prefabricated modular structures [10], turned out to be less by approximately 10–12 %. Mainly due to the ease of installation and the absence of the need to use lifting mechanisms.

The potential application of the prefab structures presented above will be interesting for regional developers who are constructing fast-erecting buildings in harshly continental natural and climatic conditions. These developers may include both subsoil users and builders of shift settlements, as well as representatives of the armed forces, medical institutions, etc.

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